

A Research Paper on “Overview on Online Digital Marketing”

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ABSTRACT

Online marketing is the art and science of selling products and / or services on digital networks such as the Internet and cellular phone networks.

The strategies of appealing strategies to target your target market in online marketing arts will be researched and actually translated into online marketing mix.

Online marketing is the science research and analysis that selects online marketing strategies to measure the success and use of online marketing strategies.

Online marketing uses the internet to deliver promotional marketing messages to customers. It includes email marketing, search engine marketing, social media marketing, display advertising (including web banner advertising), and mobile advertising. Like other advertising media, online advertisements often

include both publishers, which integrate ads into their online content and advertisers, which provide advertisements to be displayed on publisher content. Other potential participants include advertising agencies that help in generating and transferring advertising, the advertising server that delivers advertising and track statistics, and advertising affiliates who do independent promotional work for advertisers.

INTRODUCTION

Development of internet marketing is essential for the development of online marketing. Internet technology numbers are increasing in the number of Internet users worldwide in large quantities. India has settled with 81 million Internet users in 2010.¹

¹(www.internetworldstats.com)

Source: www.internetworldstats.com/top20.htm - June 30, 2010
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Fig 1 Top 20 countries with highest number of internet users

Online marketing is becoming increasingly important for all types of small businesses. In the past, marketing was something online that could ignore local brick-mortar businesses fairly. When all your business was local, it was in no way a waste of time and money on online marketing.

Now it is important by raising local discoveries and new habits of finding people on the Internet.

Online marketing is a set of powerful tools and methods used to promote products and +services through the Internet. Due to the additional channels in online marketing and the marketing mechanisms available on the Internet, there is a wide range of marketing elements from traditional business marketing.

A few specific contributions have been given in the development of online marketing -

- Online marketing can offer many benefits such as:
 - Potential development
 - Low cost
 - Elegant Communication
 - Better control
 - Improved customer service
 - Competitive Advantage

Online marketing is also known as Internet Marketing, Web Marketing, Digital Marketing and Search Engine Marketing (SEM).

If you have a brick-mortar store, you know that creating an image is a key to bringing customers. So why online branding is essential.

The com score reports that the average American passes 32 hours per month. 42% of Americans report watching TV while browsing the Internet. Having

Compatible messaging in many different ways strengthens your values and brand. Offline tactics will often result in large online results.

➤ **E-commerce is not the future...it's the present**

Forbes Magazine's report states that retail is down and e-commerce is up. A clear example of the power of e-commerce comes from Macy's recent compensation. Forbes, the 154-year-old retail chain reported a 40% increase in online sales in 2011, while sales of similar stores increased by just 5.3%. Maybe you do not have a billion dollar business like Messi, but numbers do not lie. Online sales are moving retail sales.

It is safe to say e-commerce that every year there is more and more attitude. It's not too late to jump on an e-commerce train.

➤ **Online marketing is cost-effective with measurable results**

In the old days, buying a newspaper ad is a way to reach potential customers, but now, the circulation of the newspaper drops dramatically. However, full or half-page advertising in a local paper can still run you thousands of dollars and it can not be your target audience.

Web analytics tools allow you to track the meaningful metrics and give you the opportunity to make informative information decisions on the data and not the assumptions. Depending on the data, an ROI can determine an online campaign. If the expectations are not expected, then the data provides the logic to end this campaign.

• **Online business never sleeps**

The Internet does not have "business" hours, it is 24/7/365 open, which gives you the ability to sell, stop and most importantly sell around the clock. As mentioned above, traditional media advertising (such as newspapers and television) can cut a large net but limited limit. Online marketing is also money and saver in other ways.

Due to the spread of web-enabled smart phones, nothing has been done, but it accelerates this development. Customers do not have to have a desk to use the Internet to sit in traffic, jogging in the park or eating at dinner table, whether they have access to the company's website and online advertising.

Conclusion:-

When it comes to the computer screen and a complete online modem arrives, it is not the fastest business to adopt a change. During the Clinton days of the 1990s, the use of the Internet was often used by people as a communications device in chatrooms, and most of them were held by America America.

E-commerce started selling e-commerce goods and services online, but it was Amazon before, and eBay was still back where small (small) merchandise sold things that were difficult to find elsewhere, and wait for check and money order Seeing To reach by snail mail. This was not the most effective way of profession, and large brick and mortar ventures were not used to establish an online presence.

There is no way to easily get credit card payments online - this was before Paypal was born - why worry? Even less heard about the checkout

Cart for shopping on a computer screen? There were free websites where one can set up a store, but most businesses were fashioned in old fashion, by calling their credit card number by customer or by sending a check or money order.

The emergence of dot comes, however, was around the curve, and when they came; Business changed forever.

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